

Factors Effecting Entrepreneurial Intentions in Pakistan

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Muhammd Asif-University of Punjab Lahore Pakistan

⁽²⁾Rizwan Fareed-University of Gujrat, Lahore Pakistan

⁽³⁾Muhammad Bilal Tariq-University of Gujrat, Lahore Pakistan

⁽⁴⁾Rabia Mian-Superior University Lahore Pakistan

⁽⁵⁾Naeem Ud din-CIMS Lahore Pakistan

⁽⁶⁾Zaman Haider-Manager NCBA WCC Lahore Pakistan

Abstract

this is the time of economic crises faced by almost every country of the world. Therefore, all are in a race to overcome such crises and to establish a smooth economy. Western countries are very much successful in this mission with the help of their established systems. One of the tool which is undoubtedly indispensable for economic growth is entrepreneurial activities. Hence, it has established roots in developed countries but as far as developing countries are concerned they are still suffering to reach that place. Entrepreneurship is considered to be a strong contributor in economic growth of any country. The world has started to realize its importance and therefore adopting multiple new methodologies in order to enhance entrepreneurship. According to Drucker (2002), entrepreneurship is an act that can be learned from systematic analysis of opportunities prevalent in the environment through experiential learning.

Introduction

i. Research Objective:

The main three objectives of the current research are the following;

1. Consequences of attitude towards behavior, Subjective norms and perceived behavioral control on entrepreneurial intentions in Pakistan.
2. Comparison of the height of entrepreneurial intentions among different academic disciplines.
3. Comparison of the height of entrepreneurial intentions among the students of private and public sector universities of Pakistan.

ii. Research Questions:

- ✓ What would be the consequences of attitude towards behavior, Subjective norms and perceived behavioral control on entrepreneurial intentions in Pakistan?
- ✓ How would we compare the height of entrepreneurial intentions among different academic disciplines?
- ✓ What would be the comparison of the height of entrepreneurial intentions among the students of private and public sector universities of Pakistan?

iii. Significance of the study:

In Pakistan the entrepreneurial activity is growing but at a very slow rate. Hence, Pakistan is harshly suffering from various economic challenges due to ill structured small businesses & entrepreneurial side. It is found that Pakistan is placed among factor driven economies in contrast of innovation driven economies and efficiency driven economies (GEM, 2010).

iv. Delimitations of the study:

- ✓ This study is geographically restricted and therefore it is only conducted in Lahore region due to time and resources constraints.
- ✓ In this research Ajzen theory of planned behavior is not fully applied. For determining entrepreneurial behavior longitudinal study is required which is not appropriate for this research.

2. Literature review:

- **Previous relevant literature:**

This section encompasses review of the research already done in past and then the concerned dependent variable- entrepreneurial intention and three independent variables- attitude towards the behaviour, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control based on Ajzen (1990) theory of planned behaviour. There are three objectives of this research and literature is aligned with these three objectives:

1. Effect of Attitude towards behaviour, Subjective norms and perceived behavioural control on entrepreneurial intentions using Ajzen's theory of planned behaviour model of entrepreneurial intentions in Pakistan
2. To compare level of entrepreneurial intentions of students related to disciplines of business, IT, engineering and economics in Pakistan
3. To compare level of entrepreneurial intentions among students of public and private sector universities in Pakistan

In order to understand concept of entrepreneurial intentions, it is important to know origin and meanings of entrepreneur and entrepreneurship through different researchers.

- **Hypothesis development:**

Following hypothesis can be developed;

H₁: The high level of attitudes towards the behavior increases entrepreneurial intentions among students.

H₂: The high degree of perceived behavioral control increases entrepreneurial intentions among students

H₃: The subjective norm positively influences the entrepreneurial intentions among students.

H_{4,1}: The subjective norm positively influences attitude towards the behavior among students.

H_{4,2}: The attitude towards the behavior positively influences subjective norm among students.

H_{5,1}: The subjective norm positively influences the perceived behavioral control among students.

H_{5,2}: The perceived behavioral control positively influences the subjective norm among students.

- **Theoretical framework:**

Making selection about career is actually a sensitive procedure which is determined by views & experiences, which is also identified by the previous studies conducted in this regard. This study is focusing on determining entrepreneurial behavior backed by entrepreneurial intention. Several studies have been done considering individuals' entrepreneurial intentions by understanding the entrepreneurial process (Autio et al., 2001; Davidsson, 1995; Krueger & Brazeal, 1994; Peterman & Kennedy, 2003; Shapero, 1982; Zhao et al., 2005).

3. Methodology:

- **Population of the study:**

The population for this research comprises on students from public and private sector universities of Lahore city.

- **Sample selection:**

The undergraduate students who are in their final year are selected as a sample.

- **Sample size:**

-

Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) mentioned that in regression analysis the sample size should be $N \geq 50 + 8 * M$ in which “M” shows the number of independent variables.

The current study comprises three independent variables and requires to run regression so according to described formula sample size should be 74 and it is 300 much more than the calculated.

- **Sample technique:**

Since two sectors, public and private and four disciplines Engineering, Information Technology and Economics are involve under the big umbrella of education system. Therefore, stratified sampling is the most appropriate sampling technique.

- **Unit of analysis:**

Individuals (students).

Type of study: The present study is mainly descriptive and explanatory in nature. As explanatory studies look for explanations of the nature of specific relationships. The focus in explanatory research is on studying a situation that how variables are related with each other (Hair, Babin, Money & Samouel 2003). It is descriptive in a sense that descriptive information has been collected through detailed questionnaire like demographics.

- **Time horizon:**

This research is a One-shot or cross-sectional survey because the whole data is collected only once in a time of one month.

- **Instrument development/selection (adopted/adapted give reference):**

The questionnaire developed by Liñán and Chen in 2009 is used for data collection purpose. They develop this instrument to particularly measuring entrepreneurial intention and its factors. It is known as The Entrepreneurship Intentions Questionnaire (EIQ). Likewise, the aim of this study is also measuring entrepreneurial intention. Therefore, this tool is most appropriate for this research.

- **Data collection procedure:**

First of all cover letter is issued from respective department describing the details about the purpose of research. It has been shown to the respective departments of the selected public and private sector universities before distributing questionnaires. There is no issue of anonymity and confidentiality of participants because questionnaire does not require any kind of such information which may lead to mishandling. Afterwards, questionnaires were distributed to participants of each department one by one. Each

university has taken around 4 to 5 days in assembling information from four disciplines. This process took almost 25 to 30 days in collecting whole data.

○ **Type of data:**

Primary data is collected from students of professional education which includes IT, business, engineering and economics from universities of public (University of the Punjab, GCU and COMSATS) and private (LUMS, UCP) sectors.

○ **Data analysis technique:**

- In analyses with respect to three objectives correlation, linear regression, one way ANOVA and T-tests were applied.

4. Empirical Analysis

✓ **Demographics**

In demographics, participant's information related to gender, age, parents' education and occupation, total monthly income, institute, studying degree and their work experience are included. The following table is provided with detailed information.

Table 1: Demographics of respondents with frequencies and percentages

		Frequency	Percentage
Sector	Public	179	52%
	Private	159	48%
Gender	Male	214	63.3%
	Female	124	36.7%
Age	18 to 21 years	146	43%
	22 to 25 years	188	56%
	26 to 28 years	4	1%
Year of degree completion	2013	143	42.3%
	2014	143	42.3%
	2015 or more	52	15.4%
Parents' Education	Mother		
	Primary	31	9.17%
	Secondary	78	23.1%
	Vocational	46	13.61%
	University	131	38.76%
	Other	52	15.38%
	Father		
	Primary	9	2.66%
	Secondary	62	18.34%
	Vocational	32	9.46%
Parents' Occupation	University	207	61.24%
	Other	28	8.28%
	Mother		
	Private	16	4.73%
	Public	31	9.17%
	Entrepreneur	35	10.35%
	Retired	12	3.55%
	Other (House wife)	244	72.18%
	Father		
	Private	83	24.55%
Public	75	22.18%	
Entrepreneur	133	39.35%	

	Retired	28	8.28%
	Other	19	5.62%
Family Size	2 to 5 (members)	137	40.53%
	6 to 9	185	54.73%
	10 to 13	8	2.36%
	14 and above	8	2.36%
	Total Household Income	UptoRs. 5,000	1
	Rs. 5,000 to 1k	1	0.30%
	Rs. 1k to 2k	23	6.80%
	Rs. 2k to 4k	54	16%
	Rs. 4k to 7k	82	24.26%
	Rs. 7k to 10k	103	30.47%
	Above Rs. 10k	74	21.89%
Know any Entrepreneur	In Family	79	23.37%
	Friend	6	1.78%
	Boss	6	1.78%
	Family & Friend	53	15.68%
	Family & Boss	11	3.25%
	Friend & Boss	6	1.78%
	All of them	31	9.17%
	None	146	43.20%
	Working Experience	Yes	118
No		220	65%

From the above table it can be seen that data is more weighted towards male participants than female. One reason is the normal classes are comprised with more male students in public and private sectors. Secondly male students were found to be more willing in participation. From the descriptive, 214 were male and 124 were female (n = 338).

Considering the age, 98.8% of students are of age 18 to 25, the expected age group was also 20 to 24 and it is very near to expectation. There the final year graduation students were considered.

It was tried to get the sample of last year students who are either in their second last semester or in last semester. Therefore, 84.6% students will be graduated by the following year.

If we see, participants' knowledge about any entrepreneur is very low. They hardly know any entrepreneur in their close surrounding. The above table is clearly showing that maximum number of participants do not even know any entrepreneur (146 out of 338, 43%). Therefore, influence of others on entrepreneurial intentions is not enough. Secondly inside family entrepreneurs have comparatively more weightage (79 out of 192 those know any entrepreneur).

An interesting pattern exists in parents' occupation. It can be seen in the Table 1. There is almost opposite combination of occupations exist in father and mother occupations. By considering father's occupation first, comparatively they are more involved in self-employment (39%) but on the other side mothers are mostly unemployed or housewives. So if parent's occupation is contributing in developing EI that would be from father's side.

Total household monthly income is calculated by adding up all revenues from any person living in the household. The highest income slot is 70,000 to 100,000 (103 out of 338). Therefore on average the families of these students' income ranges from 40,000 to 100,000 (55%).

The normal participants' family size is 6 to 9 (185 out of 338, 55%) members and very few families have very large family sizes. Therefore, 95% respondents have family members from minimum 2 to maximum 9.

Considering maximum level in respondents parents education, it shows that majority of both parents have university level education (61% of father, 39% of mothers). Parent's education is considered to be a contribution in developing EI in their children.

Almost half number of students has any working experience (35% as compared to 65%). This is because they have not yet started their professional life and most of them have only internship experience. Secondly data is consisted of multidisciplinary students (Business, Engineering, IT, Economics) and in most of the disciplines there is no requirement of internship, therefore they do not even have this internship experience.

Descriptive analysis:

First of all in analysis, descriptive information is collected to get the overview of the data. It is a helpful tool in data storage and in accurately summarizing information (Huysamen, 1990). Data frequency and percentages of demographics are calculated by using univariate analyses. According to Rubin & Babbie (2010), this technique in quantitative analysis includes frequency distribution, mean, mode, median and standard deviation. Demographics include gender, age, and place of birth, parents' studies, parents' occupation, household income, participant's education level, experience and entrepreneurial knowledge. The mean and standard deviations are calculated along with their frequencies.

Analysis

This research has two objectives and for fulfilling these objectives there is a need to run two different techniques.

Objective 1: To find the relationship and impact of independent variables (ATB, SN, PBC) on dependent variable (EI).

In this section the hypothesis are tested which were defined in theoretical framework by using linear regression.

Objective 2: Entrepreneurial Intention in multiple disciplines and their comparison with each other.

It involves comparative analysis of Entrepreneurial intentions among students studying in different disciplines (Business, IT, Engineering, Economics). In this case one way ANOVA is used.

Objective 3: Comparison of Entrepreneurial Intention between Public and Private Sector Universities.

In this objective comparative analysis is done among public and private sector universities to measure the difference in Entrepreneurial Intention.

Regression Analysis

To find the relationship and impact of independent variables (ATB, SN and PBC) on dependent variable (EI).

Table 2: Hypothesis for testing by using linear regression

H ₁ (ATB→EI)	<i>The high level of attitudes towards the behaviour increases entrepreneurial intentions among students.</i>
H ₂ (PBC→EI)	<i>The high degree of perceived behavioural control increases entrepreneurial intentions among students.</i>
H ₃ (SN→EI)	<i>The subjective norm positively influences the entrepreneurial intentions among students.</i>
H _{4.1} (SN→ATB)	<i>The subjective norm positively influences attitude towards the behaviour among students.</i>
H _{4.2} (ATB→SN)	<i>The attitude towards the behaviour positively influences subjective norm among students.</i>

H _{5.1} (SN→PBC)	<i>The subjective norm positively influences the perceived behavioural control among students.</i>
H _{5.2} (PBC→SN)	<i>The perceived behavioural control positively influences the subjective norm among students.</i>
H _{6.1} (ATB→PBC)	<i>Attitude towards the behaviour positively influences perceived behavioural control among students.</i>
H _{6.2} (PBC→ATB)	<i>Perceived behavioural control positively influences attitude towards the behaviour among students.</i>

In order to apply the multiple regressions the whole data is required to divide into multiple data sets because the questionnaire contains some choice based responses (Yes/No). Therefore, to analyze, the whole data is divided into four data sets. The data sets have been made on the following criteria.

The measures Q26_PBC (Have you taken any course or module that could be considered as entrepreneurship education? Yes/No) and Q28_PBC (Do you have any selection of market sector in which you are planning to operate? Yes/No). These two measures have further responses on the bases of one of the selected option yes or no. therefore; four possible data sets are made.

Table 3: Division table of complete data into sub data sets

Data Sets

Data Set 1 (YY)	When participants selected option 'yes' in both questions (Q26_PBC and Q28_PBC).
Data Set 2 (YN)	When participants selected option 'yes' in question Q26_PBC and 'no' in Q28_PBC.
Data Set 3 (NY)	When participants selected option 'no' in question Q26_PBC and 'yes' in Q28_PBC.
Data Set 4 (NN)	When participants selected option 'no' in both questions (Q26_PBC and Q28_PBC).

Now each data set is taken one by one and passes through the analysis.

Correlation

The relationship between entrepreneurial intention (EI), Attitude towards behaviour (ATB), Perceived behavioural control (PBC) and Social norms (SN) was investigated by using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient. Before performing the correlation its assumptions had verified. The assumptions of linearity and homoscedasticity were checked by generating scatterplot and graph showed a straight line, no curve had been seen which proved linearity. The graph also showed an even cigar shape along its length so the assumption of homoscedasticity is also not violated. The assumption of normality is also confirmed by drawing histogram. As the normality is proved so the Pearson product-moment coefficient is the appropriate test to be used.

Table 4: Correlations for Data Set I (YY).

Sector		PBC	SN	ATB	EI
Public	PBC Pearson Correlation	1			
	SN Pearson Correlation	.869**	1		
	ATB Pearson Correlation	.833**	.830**	1	

	EI Pearson Correlation	.530**	.541**	.575**	1
	Mean	76.0517	45.8103	89.1552	25.3276
	Standard Deviation	14.56314	10.25543	17.05903	5.69514
Private	PBC Pearson Correlation	1			
	SN Pearson Correlation	.558**	1		
	ATB Pearson Correlation	.688**	.626**	1	
	EI Pearson Correlation	.425**	.549**	.597**	1
	Mean	72.6889	42.6889	87.8667	25.1333
	Standard Deviation	11.35146	8.26224	14.73647	6.75076

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

After correlation analysis a strong positive correlation has been found between EI and PBC [$r= 0.530$, $n=58$, $p<0.01$] in public sector similarly in private sector this correlation is slightly lower [$r=0.425$, $n=45$, $p<0.01$]. Additionally SN [$r= 0.541$, $n=58$, $p<0.01$] and ATB [$r= 0.575$, $n=58$, $p<0.01$] have significant relationship with EI in public sector as well as in private sector ATB [$r= 0.549$, $n=45$, $p<0.01$] and SN [$r= 0.597$, $n=45$, $p<0.01$]. In public sector PBC [$r= 0.833$, $n=58$, $p<0.01$] and SN [$r= 0.830$, $n=58$, $p<0.01$] have very strong positive relationship with ATB but in private sector PBC [$r= 0.688$, $n=45$, $p<0.01$] and SN [$r= 0.626$, $n=45$, $p<0.01$] are also strongly correlated with ATB but lower than public sector. Furthermore SN and PBC have significant relationship with [$r= 0.869$, $n=58$, $p<0.01$] in public also with [$r= 0.558$, $n=45$, $p<0.01$] in private sector but both sectors significantly differ in strength of relationship.

Conclusion:

The role of entrepreneurship in every economy is vital and strongly recognized. Therefore, an effort was made through this study to contribute in flourishing the entrepreneurial activities in Pakistan. Here, the factors were traced those can play a significant role in enhancing the entrepreneurial intentions among students. In this research the Ajzen's theory of planned behaviour was applied on students, selected from five public and private sector universities. It was found a strong relationship between attitude towards behaviour, subjective norms, perceived behavioural control and entrepreneurial intention as well as the indirect impact of these three independent variables in developing entrepreneurial intentions through enhancing the effect of other variables. It was found that attitudes towards entrepreneurial behaviour in a person based on the intentions he has by possessing certain personal abilities, experiences or entrepreneurial education. Similarly it is seen that in society the acceptance of entrepreneurial career also encourage students to utilize their creative abilities in exploiting opportunities. In the same way, perceived behaviour control is also a very strong contributor in establishing entrepreneurial intention. It proves that if environment is supportive in terms of finances, education or market opportunities it will enhance the entrepreneurial intentions among students and they will show the entrepreneurial behaviour. Two comparative studies were also conducted in this research. In the first study, the comparison between multidisciplinary students were done in order to determine the difference in their entrepreneurial intention levels. The second study was conducted to find out if any difference exist between public and private sector universities in Lahore. In both comparative studies no differences were found. Students from all disciplines showed almost same level of entrepreneurial intentions and similarly both sectors' university students have almost same intentional level for venture creation.

References

- A. Fayolle & H. Klandt (Eds.), *International Entrepreneurship Education - Issues and Newness* (pp. 241-262). Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar.
- Adya, M. & Kaiser, K.M. (2005). 'Early determinants of women in the IT workforce: a study of Indian women', *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, Volume 2 Issue 4, PP.36-44
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behaviour. *Organizational Behaviour and Human Performance*, Vol. 4, pp. 142-75.
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (1980). *Understanding attitudes and predicting social behavior*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Aldrich, H.E. (1979), *Organizations and Environments*, Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ.
- Ali, A., Topping, K.J., Tariq, R.H. (2011). Entrepreneurial Attitudes among Potential Entrepreneurs, *Pak. J. Commer. Soc. Sci.*, Vol. 5 (1), 12-46
- Aral, S. (2010). Identifying Social Influence: A Comment on Opinion Leadership and Social Contagion in New Product Diffusion, *Marketing science Articles in Advance*, pp. 1-7
- Axelrod R. (1986). An evolutionary approach to norms. *American Political Science Review* 80(4), pp. 1095-1111
- Azahr, A., Javaid, A., Rehman, M., Hyder, A. (2011), Entrepreneurial intentions in business students in Pakistan, *Journal of Business System, Governance and Ethics*, Vol 5, no 2
- Baumol, W.J. (1990), "Entrepreneurship: productive, unproductive, and destructive", *Journal of Political Economy*, Vol. 98 No. 5, pp. 893-921.
- Bird, B. (1988). "Implementing entrepreneurial ideas: The case for intentions", *Academy of Management Review*, 13, pp. 442-454.
- Boyd, N.G. & Vozikis, G.S. (1994), "The Influence of self-efficacy on the development of entrepreneurial intentions and actions", *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, Vol. 18 No. 4, pp. 63-90.
- Bruni, A., Gherardi, S. and Poggio, B. (2004), "Entrepreneur-mentality, gender and the study of women entrepreneurs", *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, Vol. 17, pp. 256-68.
- Brush, C.G. (1992), "Research on women business owners: past trends, a new perspective and future directions", *Entrepreneurship Theory & Practice*, Vol. 16, pp. 5-30.
- Byrant, P. (2007), "Self-regulation and decision heuristics in entrepreneurial opportunity evaluation and exploitation", *Management Decision*, Vol. 45 No. 4, pp. 732-45.
- Carsrud A, Krueger N, Brännback M, Kickul J, Elfving J (2007) *The Family Business Pipeline: Where Norms and Modeling Make a Difference*. Paper presented at Academy of Management Conference Commission of the European Communities. 2003. Green Paper Entrepreneurship in Europe, Enterprise Publications.
- Carsrud, A. L., & Johnson, R. W. (1989). *Entrepreneurship: a social psychological perspective*. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development: An International Journal*, 1(1), 21-31.
- Chandler, G. N., & Jansen, E. (1992). The founder's self-assessed competence and venture performance. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 7(3), 223-236.

Conner, M., & Armitage, C. J. (1998). Extending the theory of planned behavior: a review and avenues for further research. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 28(15), 1429-1464.

Davidsson, P. (1995). Determinants of entrepreneurial intentions, *Paper prepared for the RENT IX Workshop, Piacenza, Italy*

De Carolis, D. M., & Saporito, P. (2006). Social capital, cognition, and entrepreneurial opportunities: a theoretical framework. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 30(1), 41-56.

De Carolis, D.M. and Saporito, P. (2006), "Social capital, cognition, and entrepreneurial opportunities: a theoretical framework", *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, Vol. 30 No. 1, pp. 41-56.

Dohse, D., Walter, S.G. (2010). The role of entrepreneurship education and regional context in forming entrepreneurial intentions

Drucker, P. F. (1985). *Innovation and Entrepreneurship: Practice and Principles*. New York, USA: HarperBusiness

DuRietz, A. and Henrekson, M. (2000), "Testing the female underperformance hypothesis", *Small Business Economics*, Vol. 14, pp. 1-10.

Duygu Turker, D., Sonmez Selcuk, S.S. (2008). Which factors affect entrepreneurial intention of University students? *Journal of European Industrial Training* Vol. 33 No. 2, pp. 142-159

Fagenson, E. and Marcus, E. (1991), "Perceptions of the sex-role stereotypic characteristics of entrepreneurs: women's evaluations", *Entrepreneurship Theory & Practice*, Vol. 15, pp. 33-47.

Annexure (A developed questionnaire (Liñán & Chen, 2009) was used as survey instrument)

Questionnaire

Personal Data

Gender Male Female

Age: _____

Place of birth: _____

Place of residence: _____

Number of people living in your household (including yourself): _____

What level of studies have your parents reached?

Father: Primary Secondary Vocational training University Other

Mother: Primary Secondary Vocational training University Other

What are your parents' present occupations?

Father: Private sector Public sector self-employed employee or entrepreneur

Retired Unemployed Other

Mother: Private sector Public sector self-employed employee or entrepreneur

Retired Unemployed Other

Roughly speaking, what is the **total monthly** income in your household? (adding up all revenues from any person living in the household)

Up to Rs.5,000 From Rs.5,000 to Rs.10,000 From Rs.10,000 to Rs.20,000 From Rs.20,000 to Rs.40,000

From Rs.40,000 to Rs.70,000 From Rs.70,000 to Rs.100,000 Over Rs.100,000

Education and Experience

1.	Choose your institution <input type="checkbox"/> LUMS <input type="checkbox"/> COMSATS <input type="checkbox"/> UCP <input type="checkbox"/> UET <input type="checkbox"/> PU <input type="checkbox"/> GCU <input type="checkbox"/> Others _____								
2.	What degree are you studying? <input type="checkbox"/> BBA/MBA <input type="checkbox"/> BE(Engineering) <input type="checkbox"/> IT <input type="checkbox"/> BS(Economics) <input type="checkbox"/> Others _____								
3.	When do you expect to finish it? <input type="checkbox"/> This year (2013) <input type="checkbox"/> Next year (2014) <input type="checkbox"/> Later (2015 or more)								
4.	Indicate the importance of the following reasons to choose this degree, from 1 (no important at all) to 7 (highly important)								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
	a. Vocation								
	b. Career opportunities								
	c. Advise from family or friends								
5.	Have you got working experience or done internship in any organization (have worked or are working presently)? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No If yes: a. In what position? (if several, where stayed longer) _____ b. Have you been in charge of other people? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No c. How long is it since you left your last job position? (number of years, if still working in very first organization write 0) _____ d. What size was the firm in which you worked (number of employees)? (if several, where stayed longer) _____ e. How much total experience do you have? (total number of years) _____								

Entrepreneurial knowledge

6.	Do you personally know any entrepreneur? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No If yes, indicate your relationship with them, and value the following questions from 1 (to no extent) to 7 (completely).								
	Family	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
	a. To what extent do you know his/her activity as an entrepreneur?								
	b. To what extent may he/she be considered a “good entrepreneur”?								
	Friend								
	a. To what extent do you know his/her activity as an entrepreneur?								
	b. To what extent may he/she be considered a “good entrepreneur”?								
	Boss / foreman								
	a. To what extent do you know his/her activity as an entrepreneur?								
	b. To what extent may he/she be considered a “good entrepreneur”?								
	Others								
	a. To what extent do you know his/her activity as an entrepreneur?								
	c. To what extent may he/she be considered a “good entrepreneur”?								
7.	For each of the following measures to support firm creation, indicate your level of detailed knowledge from 1 (absolute ignorance) to 7 (complete knowledge)								
		1							
	a. What are the basic trainings for new entrepreneur								
	b. How the Loans will be available for starting a business								

	c. Technical aid to start the business										
	d. What are Business centres										
	e. What are Consulting services										

Personality Traits

Indicate your level of agreement with the following sentences from 1 (total disagreement) to 7 (total agreement)									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
8.	A career as entrepreneur is attractive for me								
9.	Being an entrepreneur would entail great satisfactions for me								
10.	Other people think that I am very keen and concentrated on my approach to become entrepreneur.								
11.	I'm not willing to take risks when choosing a job or a company to work for								
12.	I view risk at work as a situation to be avoided at all costs.								
13.	I'm prepared to start a viable firm								
14.	What would you like to do immediately after finishing your degree? Value the following options from 1 (minimum preference) to 7 (maximum preference) .								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
	a. Working as an employee								
	b. Starting-up a firm								
	c. Follow on training and preparation								

Entrepreneurial Aims

Indicate your level of agreement with the following sentences from 1 (total disagreement) to 7 (total agreement)									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
15.	Competing hard in world markets								
16.	Reaching a high level of income								
17.	Helping to solve the problems of my community								
18.	Keeping a path of positive growth								
19.	If you ever started a firm, what size would you like it to achieve (number of employees)? <input type="checkbox"/> Self-employed (no employees) <input type="checkbox"/> Micro-enterprise(up to 10 employees) <input type="checkbox"/> Small enterprise (10 to 50 employees) <input type="checkbox"/> Medium enterprise (50 to 250 employees) <input type="checkbox"/> Large enterprise (over 250 employees.)								

Subjective Norms

20.	In your closest environment, do you think the entrepreneurial activity is valued worse or better than other activities and careers? Indicate from 1 (much below others) to 7 (much above others) .								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
	a. In your close family								
	b. Among your friends								
	c. Among your colleagues and class mates								
21.	If you decided to create a firm, people in your close environment would approve your decision? Indicate from 1 (total disapproval) to 7 (total approval)								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
	a. Your close family								
	b. Your friends								

	c. Your colleagues and class mates							
	Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements from 1 (total disagreement) to 7 (total agreement)							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
22.	Entrepreneurial activity clashes with the culture in my country							
23.	The entrepreneur's role in the economy is not sufficiently recognized							
24.	It is commonly thought that entrepreneurs take advantage of others							
Perceived behavioural control								
25.	To what extent do you think the following factors are supporting your entrepreneurial behaviour 1 (no extent) to 7 (completely)							
	a. National public funding							
	b. International public funding							
26.	Have you taken any course or module that could be considered as entrepreneurship education? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No If yes: I. Indicate which one(s): _____ II. To what extent has it helped you develop any of those aspects? Indicate from 1 (to no extent) to 7 (to a great extent)							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	a. Knowledge about the entrepreneurial environment							
	b. Greater recognition of the entrepreneur's figure							
	c. The preference to be an entrepreneur							
	d. The necessary abilities to be an entrepreneur							
	e. The intention to be an entrepreneur							
27.	Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements from 1 (total disagreement) to 7 (total agreement)							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	a. Possibility to access academic laboratories and equipment							
	b. Synergies between public research institutions and private firms							
28.	Do you have any selection of market sector in which you are planning to operate? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No If yes: In the market you are planning to operate, are there great differences among the product/service in following aspects with regard to (1=about the same for all products; 7=varies a great deal from one line to another)							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	a. Customers' buying habits							
	b. The nature of the competition							
	c. Market dynamism and uncertainty							
29.	Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements from 1 (total disagreement) to 7 (total agreement)							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	a. Growth opportunities in the environment are increasing							
	b. Rate of innovation of new operating processes and new products or services in your interested industry has increased dramatically.							

	c. Research and development (R&D) activity in concerned industry has substantially increased.							
Entrep reneuri al Intentio n								
30.	Have you ever seriously considered becoming an Entrepreneur? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No							
	Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements from 1 (total disagreement) to 7 (total agreement)							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
31.	I'm ready to make anything to be an entrepreneur							
32.	My actual professional goal is becoming an entrepreneur							
33.	I will make every effort to start and run my own firm							
8.	I have very seriously thought in starting a firm							
9.	I've got the firm intention to start a firm some day							